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PARENTS' VALUE

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Abstract: A woman is a unique blessing. The main role of parents in raising children.

Keywords: The importance of a mother in raising children. A person who is kind to children.

The family is a sacred place, a great blessing and a source of education. The family is a source of love, unity, harmony, respect and kindness. The main task of the family is to raise a healthy generation.

The family is the most important and primary particle of society. And it is not just a particle, but a union of living beings. The third, continuous world, consisting of the union of two worlds - a husband and a wife, is a child.

The role and influence of the family in shaping and enhancing the spirituality and abilities of a child is incomparable. Because the purest and most pure feelings of a person, the first life concepts and ideas are first formed in the family.

Among the manners that should be taught to a child: greeting when meeting, responding when calling, respecting the elderly and the younger, cleanliness, moderation, etc. Most importantly, children also learn public and social manners related to relationships with society in the family.

The one who makes a family a family is a woman. The one who unites both the family and our society, brings blessings to it, and illuminates our homes with the light of love, grace, and goodness is actually our respected mothers.

The role of parents in helping children take their rightful place in society and grow into perfect human beings is incomparable.

The role of the mother in the family is of particular importance in raising a child. No one but the mother can give the greatest feeling of love to a child. Since the most responsible task in upbringing is assigned to the mother, our mothers pay more attention to these processes and ensure that their children grow up healthy, acquire knowledge and skills, and become children who set an example for others in etiquette, morality, sincerity, and modesty.

In particular, along with learning science, they constantly enrich themselves with skills, cooking, sewing, knitting, and knowledge necessary for everyday life, this is mainly under the control of parents.

Would you believe me if I said that there are two suns in the universe? Of course not. But it really is. One sun illuminates the world with its rays in the sky, and the other one fills the hearts of all children with love in the name of Mother. If we think about it, the service of both is great and one. A mother is the one who makes a house shine. It is very difficult to describe a mother. A mother cannot be compared or equaled to anything. When you talk about a mother, the descriptions are endless, but your language is weak, words are not enough.

A mother is a great figure who loves all her children equally, who can embrace and love them all. A mother is a pillar who, when your mood is spoiled by your insignificant reason, abandons her worries and holds your hand.

A person who does not leave you even when you are alone.

As the poet Muhammad Yusuf said:

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Somehow, my heart is broken
Even though this unyielding head is bowed
Tears rise in my eyes
Can't bear this situation
A quarrelsome mother cries
The rest cry lies.

Throughout my eighteen years of life, I have been convinced of one thing, that only your own mother truly does not change. Even when her face is wrinkled and her hair is gray, she is the only person who never changes and never fakes her love and affection for you.

In life, your parents give you love with beautiful words. We don't know their kindness and love at the right time. We think of our parents' worrying words, "My child, it's cold outside, dress warmer! Don't stay out too long when it's late!", as words we tell our young children.

But one day, we want to dedicate our whole lives to listening to their stories for a moment. Appreciate your mothers whenever you have them.

Maternal love, motherly love, no matter what it is, is one of the truly human qualities.

A woman is the beauty of a home, the decoration of life.

Those who unite both the family and our society, bring blessings to it, and illuminate our homes with the light of love, elegance, and goodness are actually our trusted mothers.

With their care, hard work, and generosity of heart, intelligent and beautiful women maintain the balance, purity, honesty, sincerity, and justice in the family, and in the entire society.

The beauty of the family is, first of all, a woman.

There is a good saying that says, "When a woman laughs, the world laughs." The power that makes a woman happy is, first of all, the respect and attention she receives from her family and, lastly, at work.

For a family to be strong, a beautiful virtue called loyalty must prevail.

Yes, the qualities of purity, loyalty, fidelity, humility, and intelligence make our eastern women even more beautiful and charming. Where morality reigns, there is a special grace and freshness. Such is the role of a mother-mother.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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